

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Germany: An Introduction

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Local governments in Germany are territorial entities and their existence is therefore based on the territory allocated to them. Territorial reforms like amalgamations are therefore an encroachment on their territorial sovereignty and therefore need to be justified under the right to local self-government (Article 28(2) of the Basic Law [BL]). Detailed regulations on the admissibility of territorial changes can be found in the Local Codes. A distinction must be made between voluntary territorial changes, which can be brought about by public law contracts, and compulsory territorial changes, which require a law. The intensity of the intervention also varies depending on whether it involves the dissolution of local governments (*Auflösung*), the merger of two (or more) local governments into a new local government (*Verschmelzung*), the incorporation of one local government into the territory of the other local government (*Eingemeindung*) or the separation of individual parts of a local government (*Ausgliederung*). Counties are associations of municipalities (*Gemeindeverbände*) in the constitutional sense which is why they also have the right of self-government according to Article 28 (2)(2) BL and changes of territory must be justified beforehand. Territorial reforms at the municipal level take place periodically (in the old *Länder* last until the mid-1970s) or due to historical upheavals (as in the new *Länder*). The political objectives are to improve performance in the interests of the inhabitants and the tasks to be performed. At present, in several *Länder* (Brandenburg, Lower Saxony, Thuringia) the county level in particular is covered by territorial reforms, although some reforms have recently been announced at the municipal level (Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, Rhineland-Palatinate). Rural local governments (RLGs) rather face mergers or even dissolutions (very rare) while urban local governments' (ULGs') territory can either be expanded through incorporations or on the contrary get separated because the territory (and responsibilities) gets too unmanageable.

Inter-municipal cooperation refers to the coordinated execution of individual administrative responsibilities by the participating local bodies. Cooperation may take the form of setting up another institution (e.g. *Zweckverband*) or it may be carried out by one local government taking over the tasks for one or more other local governments. This is of course more likely to happen between RLGs, while ULGs join (not always balanced) forces with nearby RLGs to improve the urban-rural linkage. The basis for this is the respective *Länder* law. These offer various types of cooperation under public law, regulate the circle of responsibilities that are generally related to cooperation and finally lay down the basic principles of the organization. The right of each local government to cooperate with other local bodies is part of the right to self-government guaranteed by Article 28(2) BL in the form of the sovereignty to cooperate. In view of the

demographic development and the growing budget problems, voluntary and compulsory⁸⁶ inter-municipal cooperation is likely to increase in the coming years, particularly in rural areas. Even though inter-municipal cooperation represents a shift in responsibility for the performance of responsibilities, German public procurement law has provided an exception for it since 2016 (paragraph 108(6) GWB) that was already confirmed by the European Court of Justice (ECJ) earlier. In the field of public-law forms of inter-municipal cooperation a distinction must be made between the joint inter-municipal corporation (*Zweckverband*) and the public-law agreement (*öffentlich-rechtliche Vereinbarung*). The joint inter-municipal corporation is created by a public law contract between municipalities and/or counties, is institutionalized and thus itself a public territorial entity. This means that it can carry out externally effective actions in place of the otherwise competent member local governments; but it is not included in the warranty area of Article 28(2) BL. On the contrary, a public-law agreement is also concluded through a public-law contract but it arises no new institution. It has the content that one of the participants only assumes individual tasks of the other participants (delegating agreement) or undertakes to perform such tasks for the other participants (mandating agreement).

In particular, to deal especially with urban-rural problems or in conurbations, institutionalized administrative units like *Verband Region Stuttgart* and *Regionalverband Frankfurt/RheinMain* are being set up, but they may also lack the constitutional quality of Article 28(2) BL. They are typically responsible for tasks relating to transport and spatial planning, economic development and landscape design.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Pielow JC, Groneberg ST, 'Die deutschen Landkreise' (2014) 9 *Juristische Schulung* 794

Röhl HC, 'Veränderungen kommunaler Selbstverwaltung durch interkommunale Zusammenarbeit' in Hans-Günter Henneke (ed), *Kommunale Selbstverwaltung in der Bewährung* (Boorberg 2013)

⁸⁶ This is an intervention in the guarantee to local self-government that needs to be justified.

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